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FINANCIAL MECHANISMS FOR ENSURING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL TERRITORIES: NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL ASPECTS

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The article examines the role of finance in ensuring the sustainable development of rural territories in the Russian Federation. It substantiates the interconnection between the financial system and the rural economy as a key factor in implementing the state's strategic objectives. The paper analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations of the interaction between finance and sustainable development, highlighting the functioning of public, banking, cooperative, and market financing mechanisms for rural projects. Particular attention is paid to existing problems and barriers, including limited access to credit, the lack of long-term financial instruments, underdeveloped insurance mechanisms, institutional fragmentation, and legal uncertainty. Drawing on international experience, the study outlines promising directions for modernizing the financial system: the development of green and sustainable financial instruments, integration of ESG criteria, digitalization of financial services, expansion of cooperative institutions, and the creation of long-term investment mechanisms. The article concludes that a comprehensive model of financial support for sustainable rural development is required, based on the integration of public and private resources and harmonization with global trends.

Keywords: finance, rural territories, sustainable development, banking credit, green finance, ESG, public-private partnership, cooperative finance, investment, financial inclusion.

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